

EFFECT OF GLUCOSE CONTENTS OF SELECTED SOFT DRINKS ON PLASMA GLUCOSE LEVEL OF ADOLESCENT HEALTHY NIGERIAN SUBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

Soft drink is a carbonated water, flavoured and sweetened with either sugar or sweetener. The resulting glucose solution in the human body is the key source of energy. Positive associations between soft drinks consumption and incidence of diabetes have been postulated. Thus, it is the aim of this study to show the effects of casual soft drinks consumption on glucose level of healthy Nigerian individuals in fasting and 2 hours post-prandial. A total of 350 apparently healthy individuals were recruited for this study. 115 subjects (Group A) were given a bottle of Coca-Cola (Coke) each, another 115 (Group B) subjects were given a bottle of Bitter Lemon (Krest) each while the remaining 120 subjects (Group C) were given 75g of D-glucose in 300mL of distilled water. Glucose tolerance test (GTT) was performed on all the subjects and the curve of glucose concentration plotted against time of sample collection. GTT graph of group A and B shows a flat curve of enhanced GTT while group C shows a normal GTT response graph. The result however, indicates that casual consumption of soft drinks did not predispose to development of diabetes as it has no significant effect on plasma glucose and renal threshold concentration of apparently healthy individuals.

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INTRODUCTION

Soft drink is a carbonated water, flavoured and sweetened with either sugar or sweetener (Australian, 2004). Soft drinks are the beverage of choice for millions of people around the world. Some drink them in the morning, noon, and at night. They are tasty, available everywhere, and inexpensive. They are also a prime source of extra calories that can contribute to weight gain. The primary ingredient in these drinks is sugar, usually from high fructose corn syrup or cane sugar (Cespedes, 2010). Substantial evidence had suggested that higher consumption of sugar sweetened soft drinks may raise the risk of developing type 2 diabetes and carbohydrate related metabolic syndrome (obesity in both children and adults) (Malik, *et al.*, 2006). Soft drinks contain large amount of simple sugars, which can induce higher glycemic and insulinemic response and in the long run, may lead to beta cell failure (Hu, 2009). These simple sugars are majorly glucose compound containing six-carbon as the back bone and the most important fuel for both human beings and most microorganisms (RnCeus, 2012).

Glucose is by far the most common carbohydrate and classified as a monosaccharide, an aldose, a hexose, and a reducing sugar. It is known as dextrose, because it is dextrorotatory (meaning that as an optical isomer it rotates plane polarized light to the right). Glucose is the human body's key source of energy through aerobic respiration, anaerobic respiration or fermentation, providing approximately 3.75 kilocalories (16 kilojoules) of food energy per gram (Rich, 2003). Breakdown of carbohydrates (e.g. starch) yields mono and disaccharide, most of which is glucose. Through glycolysis and later in the reactions of the citric acid cycle, glucose is oxidized eventually to carbon-dioxide and water yielding energy sources, mostly in the form of ATP (SparkNotes Editors, 2012). Regulatory hormones, such as insulin, glucagons and epinephrine, maintain and regulate the concentration of glucose in human blood within a fairly narrow range under diverse conditions like feeding, fasting, or severe exercise (Stephen *et al.*, 2004). Thus, this study aimed at showing the effects of casual soft drinks consumption on glucose level of apparently healthy Nigerian individuals in fasting and 2 hours post-prandial.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and Methods

Study Population

Ile-Ife is located in the south western region of Nigeria. It is the cradle of Yoruba race. This survey was carried out within Ile-Ife Township. The town was chosen because the town was planned in a way, which made sampling and logistics for the study easier. Secondly it has a fair representation of different strata of people living in the society.

Sampling Procedures

The town was divided into 100 areas of approximately 200 housing units each, using the standard map of the town. Three clusters were randomly selected in each area. All housing units in the three selected clusters were enlisted for the study. Three hundred and fifty subjects living in the chosen units who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were eventually enlisted.

Inclusion criteria include:

- Age, between 18 and 30 years of age
- Resident in the study area of Ile-Ife Township
- Selected by the random sampling procedure
- Willing to participate and comply with the instructions of the study e.g. overnight fasting.
- Informed consent.

Exclusion criteria:

- History of use of drugs that could affect glucose metabolism e.g. steroids, B-blockers, thiazide diuretics.
- Pregnancy.
- Having diabetes or any family history of Diabetes

Study procedure

This study was done between 08:00 and 10:00h daily between January and March in the year 2010. On arrival at the study venue, each subject was allowed to rest for about 10 min, a questionnaire designed for the study was administered and subjects was given free hand to choose what type of drinks he/she desired among the three drinks, Coca-Cola, bitter lemon and D-glucose, and subsequently grouped into group A, B and C respectively.

Socio-demographic data and history of personal habits such as smoking, alcohol consumption and physical activity were obtained. Physical activity was assessed from the occupation of the individual. People who engaged in manual labour, such as farming or professional sports were classified as physically active, while those who engaged in trade, housework or nursing were classified as moderately active physically. Physically inactive people included those who did sedentary jobs, e.g. office workers, or the unemployed. Those who engaged in sedentary jobs were classified as moderately active physically if they engaged in leisure sports (Nyenwe *et al.*, 2003). Alcohol consumption was categorized as moderate or heavy based on the criteria of Obembe *et al.*, (1993), with alcohol intake of 21 units/week or more was regarded as heavy drinkers, while less than 21 units/week was regarded as moderate drinkers. The weight of the subject was measured to the nearest kilogram with a Hanson type bathroom weighing scale. The height was measured to the nearest meter. The body mass index (BMI) was calculated and recorded. Classification by BMI was done according to the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) expert committee for the classification of overweight (Seidell and Fligel, 1997). Subjects also indicated whether they are smoking or not.

Venous blood (2.0 ml) was collected each time at 30 minutes interval for 2 hour into fluoride-oxalate and transported to the Chemical Pathology Laboratory of Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital (OAUTH), Ile-Ife, on ice pack within the same day for the determination of oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT), using enzymatic method of glucose oxidase-peroxidase. Urine samples were also collected into plain universal bottles for urine glucose detection from each subject at interval of 0, 1 and 2 hour.

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Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done using SPSS software and Microsoft excel statistical package. Result was presented as mean ($\pm$ SD), glucose concentration (mmol/L) was plotted against time (hours) of blood collection for OGTT. The statistical p value was set at <0.05

Ethical consideration

This study was conducted in adherence to 2008 Helenski declaration on human experimentation. Informed consent was used in the recruitment of participants and confidentiality was maintained in accordance with standard medical practice.

RESULTS

In all 350 apparently healthy individuals aged between 18 and 30 years were recruited for this study. 115 subjects (Group A) were given 1 bottle of Coca-cola (Nigeria Bottling Company[®]) each, another 115 (Group B) individuals were given 1 bottle of Bitter Lemon (Krest-Nigeria Bottling Company[®]) each and 75g of Allenburys^(R)D-glucose (Evans) in 300ml of distilled water was given to the remaining 120 subjects (Group C – which serves as control group) each. Characteristics of each group are as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Characteristics of Test Subjects

Parameters	Groups		
	A n=115	B n=115	C n=120
Age	27.3 $\pm$ 3.60	27.08 $\pm$ 2.80	27.70 $\pm$ 2.90
Sex (Male/Female)	57/58	58/57	59/61
BMI			
< 25	65	69	65
$\geq$ 25	50	46	55
Physical Activity			
Active	78	80	88
Not-Active	37	35	32
Alcohol intake			
Not drinking	90	87	96
< 21 units/week	20	22	21
$\geq$ 25 units/week	5	6	3
Smoking			
Yes	25	28	24
No	90	87	96

Glucose concentration in Coca-Cola, Krest and 75g of D-glucose were 0.54mmol/L (0.97mg/cL), 0.40mmol/L (0.72mg/cL) and 1,377.20mmol/L (2,500mg/cL) respectively. Mean ($\pm$ SD) plasma blood glucose of the test groups as per different time of blood collection (fasting, 30min, 1hour, 1.30hour and 2hours) was as presented in Table 2.

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TABLE 2: Plasma Glucose of Groups At Different Time of Collection

Group	Fasting (mmol/L)	0.30hrs (mmol/L)	1.00hr (mmol/L)	1.30hrs (mmol/L)	2.00hrs (mmol/L)
A.	3.5(±0.63)	4.8(±0.78)	4.0(±0.61)	3.6(±0.67)	3.8(±0.57)
B.	3.5(±0.55)	4.7(±0.41)	4.0(±0.28)	3.6(±0.28)	3.2(±0.27)
C.	3.4(±0.99)	5.6(±1.08)	6.5(±1.23)	5.7(±1.52)	3.9(±1.10)

The urine samples of all the tests groups showed negative results when tested for glucose. Figure 1 shows the oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) graph of all the subjects under study.

Figure 1: Oral Glucose Tolerance Curve for All The Subjects

DISCUSSION

A simple oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) is the standard test revealing subclinical diabetes when the fasting blood glucose is normal, and it shows the ability of the body to handle the glucose load (Ranjna, 1999). This study was undertaken to determine the effect of glucose contents in Coca – Cola (Coke) and Bitter Lemon (Krest) on plasma glucose level of healthy Nigerian subjects. At zero hour, fasting blood glucose value was

within the normal range in all the three groups of subjects. This agreed with the laid down protocols for administering OGTT on an individual (Burtis and Ashwood 2000).

In the test groups A and B (subjects given Coke and Krest respectively), the peak value for glucose is seen at 0.30hrs and return back to fasting level at 1.30hrs which indicates that ingestion of soft drinks and juices tends to cause rapid increase in blood sugar and insulin relative to many other beverages and food (Andrew, 2009). The result of these two groups (A and B) is indicative of flat curve of enhanced glucose tolerance as described by Ranjna, (1999) while control group C (group given 75g of D glucose), shows peak value at 1hr and returns back to fasting level at 2hrs, (a normal response curve).

The result of this work clearly reveals that light (casual) drinkers of soft drinks (i.e. 1 bottle serving per day) are not prone to develop diabetes mellitus, a result which is in contrast to earlier reported studies that have shown association between consumption of soft drinks and increase incidence of diabetes (Schulze, *et al.*, 2004, Andrew, *et al.*, 2010, Dhingra, *et al.*, 2007, Montonen, *et al.*, 2007, Palmer, *et al.*, 2008, Yoshida, *et al.*, 2007). This work however, was in agreement with that of Paynter, *et al.*, (2006) who found no association between sweetened beverage consumption and diabetes risk. The difference found in our study and those with positive correlation with diabetes may be largely due to number of subjects and soft drinks serving per day used in our study.

CONCLUSION / RECOMMENDATION

This study reveals that light / casual consumption of soft drinks has no significant effect on plasma glucose and renal threshold concentration of glucose in apparently healthy individuals except in a potential diabetic individual which was not included in our study. Thus, consumption of soft drinks once awhile cannot cause diabetes, contrary to general opinion or believe making wave in the society that soft drink consumption can cause diabetes.

To our knowledge, this is the first study addressing the topic of soft drinks consumption and incident of type 2 diabetes in Nigerian population, thus a larger prospective study group is advocated as sedentary lifestyle and increasingly westernization has been postulated to contribute to the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus in developing countries.

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